

ANALYSIS OF CONVERSION OF ANALOG MYOELECTRIC SIGNALS TO DIGITAL

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Abstract -The electrical signals produced by muscle movement, known as myoelectric signals, can provide varied information depending on the objective and context in which they are used. They can indicate the presence of muscle activity, the intensity of contraction, or the periodicity of this activity. The analysis of these signals can be performed by capturing the entire signal over a certain period or by evaluating specific parameters such as amplitude, duration, or root mean square value. The objective of this work is to develop an analog-to-digital converter architecture using binary value sensors, based on first-order system control laws. This approach allows for the estimation of unknown system parameters, saving energy and reducing the complexity of the analog part of the circuit. It is possible to acquire signals with a resolution of 4 or 5 bits and a bandwidth limited to a few kHz.

Keywords: Analog, Digital, Myoelectrics, Conversion, Analog circuits

INTRODUCTION

Muscle activity generates electrical signals known as myoelectric signals, which have amplitudes ranging from a few microns to a few millivolts. These signals are characterized by relatively low frequencies, typically ranging from a few Hertz to around 400 Hz, and can reach 500 Hz in some individuals. Depending on the purpose and context in which they are used, different information can be extracted from these signals, such as muscle activity detection, contraction intensity, and activity periodicity. To analyze these signals, one can consider the entire signal captured during a specific period or only certain characteristic parameters, such as peak amplitude, signal duration, or root mean square value. Based on these characteristics and the desired information, signal acquisition and conditioning circuits can be determined, such as the use of an analog-to-digital converter (ADC).

Myoelectric signals can be measured through electromyography (EMG), which is a technique that uses electrodes to record the electrical activity of muscles. EMG can be used to diagnose muscle disorders, evaluate treatment effectiveness, and monitor patient progress during rehabilitation. Myoelectric signals are also important for biomechanics and biomedical engineering, as they help understand how muscles contract and how this contraction can be controlled and enhanced for various applications, such as prosthetics and assistive locomotion devices.

The conversion of analog signals to digital (ADC) is a process by which an analog signal is sampled and transformed into a digital representation that can be processed and stored in a computer or electronic device. This process is necessary in many

applications, such as audio and video systems, sensors, industrial process control, among others.

The conversion process involves sampling the analog signal at regular time intervals, followed by quantization, where each sample is rounded to the nearest digital value. The resolution of the conversion is determined by the number of bits used to represent each digital sample. The higher the number of bits, the higher the resolution and accuracy of the conversion.

There are various types of ADCs, which can be classified according to the sampling technique, quantization type, and number of bits used. The most common ADC types include successive approximation, ramp, dual-slope, delta-sigma, and flash converters. Each type of converter has its own advantages and disadvantages in terms of speed, resolution, accuracy, and cost.

After the conversion of the analog signal into digital, it can be digitally processed, stored in electronic storage devices, transmitted through digital communication networks, or converted back into an analog signal through digital-to-analog converters (DAC) for sound reproduction, image display, or control of analog devices.

DEVELOPMENT

To analyze myoelectric signals, the following steps are necessary:

Electrodes: The first step involves placing electrodes on the skin surface or inserting a needle into the muscle to collect the myoelectric signal.

Amplification: The myoelectric signal is amplified using a signal amplifier to improve its quality and make it easier to measure.

Filtering: The amplified signal is filtered to remove any noise or electrical interference that may be present in the signal.

Signal Processing: The filtered signal is processed to extract relevant information such as signal amplitude, frequency, and duration.

Analysis: The obtained data is analyzed using signal processing techniques to identify patterns and characteristics of the myoelectric signal. This may include analyzing signal amplitude, frequency, duration, as well as detecting peaks or other events in the signal.

Interpretation: Finally, the results of the analysis are interpreted to obtain information about muscle function, fatigue, the presence of muscle or neuromuscular pathologies, and other relevant aspects.

After this process, the obtained data is used for data conversion, using digital electronics logic to better understand the movements and develop a program that uses logic gates to mimic the observed movements.

To perform the above processes, the Heart Monitor [1] connected to an Arduino Uno was used, which captures the body's electrical signals in analog form through electrodes attached to the human body [2].

(Figure 1- Circuit [1])

(Figure 2 – connected electrodes [2])

And to perform the analysis, the ARDUINO IDE application was chosen. Using a programming framework [3], a range of waveforms was established for conversion into digital format, aiming to develop movement for a potential prosthesis.

```

1 // Utilizando o módulo AD 8232 de monitoramento Cardíaco - ECG
2 // Eletrocardiograma
3
4 void setup() {
5 // initialize the serial communication:
6 Serial.begin(300);
7
8 }
9
10 void loop() {
11
12 if((digitalRead(10) == 0)||((digitalRead(11) == 1)){
13 Serial.println('1');
14 }
15 else{
16 // send the value of analog input 0:
17 Serial.println(analogRead(A0));
18 }
19 //Wait for a bit to keep serial data from saturating
20 delay(1);
21 }
22

```

(Figure 3- Code used in Arduino IDE [3])

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The results obtained from the experiments conducted [4][5] show that separating the interval between 300 to 900 bauds is the best option, as the signals reached a maximum of 700 bauds. This allows us to isolate certain peaks and convert them into digital signals, such as binary codes of 0 and 1, thus forming a movement in the prosthesis similar to the human pattern. This

